

**A STUDY ON THE PREDICTIVE ABILITY OF
CLASSROOM CLIMATE AND FAMILY ATMOSPHERE ON
LIFE SKILL ATTAINMENT AND ON ACADEMIC
ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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Abstract:

Education is a process by which a person's body mind and character are formed and strengthened, thus enabling a person's holistic development of personality through knowledge. Learning performance of students can be improved by providing right content at the right time and at the right place to the right devices. Investigation in classroom climate provides a new direction in learning environment research to remove the knowledge gap that is existed in the earlier works in this field. In the process of teaching and learning, environment or condition plays significant role to a great extend. Here, environment includes the environment of the classroom as well as the environment of the school. School is the sociological unit that exerts the greatest influence on the development and perpetuation of individual's behaviour. Pierce (1994) found that a specific pattern of classroom organization had a considerable impact on the manner in which the students and teacher related to each other and on the students' performance. The success or the failure of the students also depends on the quality of classroom's social climate. Research on learning in India and abroad indicates that effective learning depends on four types of variables such as personal variables of learners, content variables, situational variables and strategy variables. So the situational variable or environmental variable is one of the influential variables of learning and shaping of behaviour. Moreover it is one of the strong sociological factors that can deeply influence academic achievement and skill attainment. Effective classroom climate practices can create a conducive learning environment that fosters the learner variables academic achievement, life skills etc. This study performed a meta-analysis and research synthesis of the Impact of Classroom climate on Life skill attainment of High school students.

Key Words: Predictive ability, Classroom Climate, Self-Efficacy, Approaches to Learning

Classroom Climate:

Classroom climate is the environment prevailed in the classroom when the process of teaching learning takes place. It is a psychological and interpersonal atmosphere inside the classroom where students feel safe, nurtured, and intellectually stimulated. A classroom is a training place for building a future society. The classroom climate moulds the students to be good citizens. Classroom climate refers to the 'Intellectual, social, emotional, and physical environments in which our students learn.' Beyond simply educating, teachers serve many other roles in the classroom. Teachers can set the tone of their classrooms, build a positive learning environment, mentor and nurture students, become strong role models and listen and look for signs of trouble. Research shows that many aspects of our classroom environment can affect student motivation and that students who are more motivated, put more effort into learning activities and life skill attainment. Classroom climate is defined as involvement, affiliation, teacher support, task orientation, competition, order and organization, rule clarity and teacher control. It is interpreted as the score obtained in the classroom climate scale.

Life Skill Attainment:

'Life skill attainment' is used to denote the abilities to achieve the skills needed to deal with the demands and challenges of everyday life. Education for personal and social development has to equip adolescents with Life skills, so that they can cope up with the challenges and pressures of life in the new age. The new kind of jobs arising from the advancement of technology needs high degree of life skill attainment. Life skills are an inevitable part of the day-to-day life, which needed for developing psychosocial competence i.e. the ability to maintain a state of well-being while interacting with others or dealing with oneself in various day to day situations. Life Skills are a group of competencies that help adolescents in goal setting, developing self-confidence and good interpersonal skills, and also essential for promotion of healthy child and adolescent development, socialization and preparing young people for changing social circumstances. Life skills such as responsibility, self-esteem, interpersonal skills and community skills may develop to its full

potential with adequate practice and professional intervention from the part of teachers and parents. Life skills education should be compulsorily made as the cornerstone of various youth programmes and should form an integral part of our formal education process.

Objective of the Study:

To find out the significant impact of Classroom on Life skill attainment of Secondary school students with regard to Total sample and Sub samples based on a). Gender (Male / Female) b). Socio-economic status (High / Average / Low)

Methodology:

The method adopted should always be valid, reliable and appropriate to the nature of the problem under investigation and the kind of data that the problem demands. The present study aims to find out the significant impact of Classroom climate on Life skill attainment of Secondary school students. For getting a clear picture of the scenario of the problem; it was intended to collect extensive and true representative data. Hence normative survey method will be adopted by the investigator for collecting the data.

Variables of the Study: The independent variable used for the present study is Classroom Climate. The dependent variables used for the present study Life skill attainment.

Sample for the Study: A sample of 400 High school students will be selected using stratified random sampling technique giving due representation to the classificatory variables.

Tools for the Study: The tools used for the collection of the data are: Classroom Climate scale, Life skill attainment scale and Socio-economic status scale

Statistical Techniques Employed: The statistical techniques used for analyzing the data are the descriptive statistics like Mean, Median, Mode, Standard deviation, and Karl Pearson’s Coefficient of Correlation analysis to find out the significant impact of Independent variable on dependent variable.

Hypothesis:

There is no significant relationship between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school students on Total sample and Subsamples based on A). Gender (Male/Female), B). Socio-economic status (High/Average/Low)

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school students for the Total sample

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of Secondary school students are analysed to find out whether any significant correlation exists among them. The data and results of the correlation analysis are given in the table 1.

Table 1: Correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school students for total sample

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
Classroom Climate	420	143.63	20.36	0.193	0.001
Life Skill Attainment	420	190.7	25.46		

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of Secondary school students are graphically presented in figure 1.

Figure 1: Mean and Standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school students on total samples

The positive correlation coefficient of 0.193 indicates that there is a weak positive relationship between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment for the total sample. As Classroom climate scores increase among the participants, the Life skill attainment scores tend to increase as well, and vice versa. This suggests that a more positive and supportive classroom climate is associated with higher levels of life skill attainment among the participants. The p-value of 0.001 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the significance level of 0.01. In conclusion, the correlation analysis indicates that there is a significant positive association between classroom climate and life skill attainment for the total sample. Participants who perceive a more positive and supportive classroom climate also tend to exhibit higher levels of life skill attainment, and vice

versa. Hence the hypothesis stated that, there is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school students for the total sample is rejected.

Hypothesis 1.A.1:

There is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school Girls

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment were analysed to find out whether any significant correlation exists among Secondary school Girls. The data and results of the correlation analysis are given in the table 2.

Table 2: Correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school Girls

Girls	Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
	Classroom Climate	210	144.67	17.48		
	Life Skill Attainment	210	186.19	26.89		

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of Secondary school Girls are graphically presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Mean and Standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school students

The positive correlation coefficient of 0.328 indicates that there is a moderate positive relationship between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment for girls. As Classroom climate scores increase among the girls, the Life skill attainment scores tend to increase as well, and vice versa. The p-value of 0.001 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the significance level of 0.01. In conclusion, the correlation analysis indicates that there is a significant positive association between classroom climate and life skill attainment for girls. Girls who perceive a more positive and supportive classroom climate also tend to exhibit higher levels of life skill attainment, and vice versa. Hence the hypothesis stated that, there is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school Girls is rejected.

Hypothesis 1.A.2:

There is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school Boys

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment were analysed to find out whether any significant correlation exists among secondary school boys. The data and results of the correlation analysis are given in the table 3.

Table 3: Correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school Boys

Boys	Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
	Classroom Climate	210	142.59	22.88		
	Life Skill Attainment	210	195.2	23.15		

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of Secondary school Boys are graphically presented in figure 3.

Figure 3: Mean and Standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school Boys

The positive correlation coefficient of 0.105 indicates that there is a very weak positive relationship between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment for boys. The r-value is close to zero, suggesting that there is minimal association between the two variables for boys. In other words, the relationship between classroom climate and life skill attainment among boys is not very strong. The p-value of 0.129 is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This means that the observed relationship between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment for boys is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis stated that, there is no significant correlation between of Secondary school students for the subsample based on boys is accepted.

Hypothesis 1.B.1:

There is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of Secondary school students with High Socio-economic status.

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment were analysed to find out whether any significant correlation exists among the High Socio-economic status groups of Secondary school students. The data and results of the correlation analysis are given in the table 4.

Table 4: Correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school students with High Socio-economic status

High Socio-Economic Status	Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
	Classroom Climate	173	147.29	20.28		
	Life Skill Attainment	173	188.89	25.37		

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of High Socio-economic status students are graphically presented in Figure 4

Figure 4: Mean and Standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among High Socio-economic status students

The positive correlation coefficient of 0.238 indicates that there is a moderate positive relationship between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment for individuals with High Socio-economic Status. As Classroom climate scores increase among individuals with High Socio-economic Status, the Life skill attainment scores tend to increase as well, and vice versa. This suggests that a more positive and supportive classroom climate is associated with higher levels of life skill attainment among individuals with High Socio-economic Status. The p-value of 0.001 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the significance level of 0.01. In conclusion, the correlation analysis indicates that there is a significant positive association between classroom climate and life skill attainment among individuals with High Socio-economic Status. Those who perceive a more positive and supportive classroom climate also tend to exhibit higher levels of life skill attainment, and vice versa, within this specific group. Hence the hypothesis stated that, there is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among the Secondary school students with High Socio-economic status is rejected.

Hypothesis 1.B.2:

There is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of Secondary school students with Average Socio-economic status

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment were analysed to find out whether any significant correlation exists among Average Socio-economic status groups of Secondary school students. The data and results of the correlation analysis are given in the table 5.

Table 5: Correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school students with Average Socio-economic status

Average Socio-Economic Status	Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
	Classroom Climate	172	144.02	20.71		
	Life Skill Attainment	172	191.47	26.70		

Mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of Average Socio-economic status students are graphically presented in figure 5.

Figure 5: Mean and Standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Average Socio-economic status students

The positive correlation coefficient of 0.284 indicates that there is a moderate positive relationship between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment for individuals with Average Socio-economic Status. As Classroom climate scores increase among individuals with Average Socio-economic Status, the Life skill attainment scores tend to increase as well, and vice versa. This suggests that a more positive and supportive classroom climate is associated with higher levels of life skill attainment among individuals with Average Socio-economic Status. The p-value of 0.001 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the significance level of 0.01. In conclusion, the correlation analysis indicates that there is a significant positive association between classroom climate and life skill attainment among individuals with Average Socio-economic Status. Those who perceive a more positive and supportive classroom climate also tend to exhibit higher levels of life skill attainment, and vice versa, within this specific group. Hence the hypothesis stated that, there is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of the Secondary school students with Average Socio-economic status is rejected.

Hypothesis 1.B.3:

There is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of Secondary school students with Low Socio-economic status

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment were analysed to find out whether any significant correlation exists among Low Socio-economic status groups of Secondary school students. The data and results of the correlation analysis are given in the table 6.

Table 6: Correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school students with Low Socio-economic status

Low Socio-Economic Status	Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
	Classroom Climate	75	134.26	16.70		
	Life skill attainment	75	193.12	22.63		

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment of Low Socio-economic status students are graphically presented in figure 6.

Figure 6: Mean and Standard deviation scores of Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Low Socio-economic status students

The negative correlation coefficient of -0.114 indicates that there is a weak negative relationship between Classroom climate and life skill attainment for individuals with Low Socio-economic Status. As Classroom climate scores increase among individuals with Low Socio-economic Status, the Life skill attainment scores tend to decrease slightly, and vice versa. However, the correlation is very close to zero, suggesting that the relationship between classroom climate and life skill attainment among individuals with Low Socio-economic Status is not very strong. The p-value of 0.328 is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This means that the observed relationship between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment for individuals with Low Socio-economic Status is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. In conclusion, the correlation analysis suggests that there is a weak negative association between classroom climate and life skill attainment among individuals with Low Socio-economic Status. However, this relationship is not statistically significant.

Hence the hypothesis stated that, there is no significant correlation between Classroom climate and Life skill attainment among Secondary school students with Low Socio-economic status is accepted.

Educational Implications of the Study:

The present research is undertaken to find out the impact of Classroom climate and on Life skill attainments of secondary school students. The Gender and Socio-economic status, are classificatory variables which considered for the categorization of subsamples. The investigator finds out the significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The findings of the study throw some light on the fact that there should be an impact of Classroom climate on students Life skill attainment. So the code of excellent Classroom climate maintaining techniques which have to be strictly follow by the teaching community to provide necessary environment for the proper development of life skill among students. The school teachers have to aware about the Classroom climate maintain strategies and acquire the necessary teaching skill to inculcate the life skill among students. The future of the children is quite safe in the hands of al skilled teacher; on the other hand if a teacher suffers from lack of excellent classroom climate maintaining skills, he is not only harming himself but doing a great harm to the children under his supervision and to the society at large. The findings of the study have profound implications for Teachers, Teacher Educators, Research Agencies, Research Scholars, Curriculum Constructors, Course Designers, and Professional Training Institution. Some of the major implications of the study are:

- National and state level curriculum framers must take adequate steps to strengthen the cordial Classroom climate for the successful teaching –learning processes in schools.
- The government and school authorities should arrange some in-service courses to teachers to maintain Classroom climate in excellent way.
- Teachers should aware about the importance of Classroom climate to avoid the anxiety and tension among students
- Teachers should maintain an excellent classroom climate to create interest among students towards learning.
- School authorities should provide proper facilities to students to develop required life skills.
- Teachers should become able in managing the classroom activities and putting his maximum effort to provide a better classroom climate to strengthen the Life skills.
- Teachers make aware their students about the new trends and challenges in attaining proper life skills to lead their future life in this highly competitive and digital world.
- Inculcate the positive attitude among teachers to face the challenges to maintain excellent classroom climate for teaching-learning processes.
- In-service and pre-service courses should be periodically revised to strengthen appropriate classroom climate maintaining strategies for the teachers.

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